
Research

Principles of Emotional Management in Theravada Jataka Stories

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Abstract: The purpose of the study is that developing Buddhist view on psychological conceptual background, help understanding the application of Buddhist literature and introducing an enhancement of emotional in-telligence. Selected 50 tales of Theravada Buddhist Jataka collection from “The book of five hundred and fifty Jataka Stories”, and they were analysed through emotional management principles in the book ‘**Practicable guide to manage Emotions**’ written by Kumarasena A.K. This study analyzed each of stories according to the book’s principles. And finally the conclusion of research hypothesis is done based on the relationship between variables. The result provides the significant correlation between Jataka stories and emotional managing techniques in Kumarasena’s book. The study suggests that following Jathaka stories as educational tool is effective method to enhance emotional abilities in people. Further researches are essential on this field to investigate psychological support of Jataka literature and Bodhisattva concept for the well-being in current communities. This research is limited to discuss only emotional function in 50 stories and further researches are needed to identify other psychological functions in all Jataka stories of Theravada Buddhist literature related to Bodhisattva concept.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, emotional principles, Theravada Jataka stories, Bodhisattva concept

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Introduction

In western psychology scholars pay their attention on human experiences of behaviour, cognition and emotion. “Modern psychologists have inebriated their research on emotion in recent decades” [1], previous scientific data explore emotional management essentially impacts a healthy life. Buddhist teaching approaches mainly focus on the function of the five aggregates of living beings (*Pamcaskhanda*); physical structures (*Rūpa*), feelings (*Vēdana*), perceptions (*Sañña*), mental constructions (*Sankāra*) and consciousness (*Viññāna*). Within Buddhist analytic five components, emotions represent from **Vēdana** and **Sankāra**. Whole Buddhist practices guide to realize the importance of emotional management at habitual tasks and development them. **Bodhisattva concept** and Jataka Stories are widely accepted in Mahayana as well Theravada Buddhist communities during two millenniums.

This study examines techniques of emotional management [2] in Theravada Buddhist Jataka stories [3]. The purpose of the study is that developing Buddhist view on Psychological conceptual background, help understanding the

application of Buddhist literature and enhance understanding of new directions of psychology. In this study, subject matter resources were investigated in details. Data through several types of psychological models is illustrated at the task on emotional function in Jataka tales.

Emotions

The field of Emotion and Motivation is one of the leading disciplines in Western psychology. The two words are derived from the Latin word '**movere**' meaning '**to move**' [4]. It is considered as '**Drive**'. That is, the force that motivates or pushes people to engage in a particular activity. Emotions are mental feelings and situations that arise in the human mind, such as fear, grief, sadness, anger, hatred and revenge. Emotions and motivations both seem to be mental states that motivate people to engage in certain behaviour.

Emotions cannot be definite, because emotion is a pleasure, so living beings like humans have the ability to hide emotions. It is difficult to determine what kind of experience they will have by looking at their behaviour. Also, moods are not objective, and one can get some idea of the meaning of the word emotion by looking at the cognitive discourse.

The English-Sinhala dictionary defines emotions as the strongest emotion, weakness, impulse, mood or emotion that arises in the mind [5]. The Buddhist dictionary defines various emotions as anger, fear, and grief that arise in the mind (Liyanage, 2005: 354). The etymological dictionary also defines anger, fear, sadness, grief, joy, and what comes to mind [5].

The Sinhala dictionary defines that a nature of the mind is emotions such as anger, love and joy [7]. The 'Dictionary of Education' also defines emotions as the state of mind in which emotions occur, the motivation and adaptation to such things, the manifestations of the real state of human pleasure, and the manifestations of the mental as well as the physical reflexes [8]. Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary has a similar definition. It depicts emotions such as love, happiness, violence, fear, jealousy, etc., as well as expressions of various mental natures such as pleasure, fear and agitation [9]. Companion Encyclopedia of Psychology explains emotion has many meanings. Among them, happiness, anger, sadness, torture, violence, panic, stress, frustration, amazement, curiosity, etc [10] are described as emotional and emotionally adaptable traits.

It is evident from the above exaggerations that emotions can be identified as a mental discipline that builds up consciously or unconsciously on the internal and external factors of a person and causes a certain movement in the mind. No definite definition of what emotions are has been identified in Western psychology. There is no clear consensus among psychologists and they too have expressed different views. Emotions are identified as a feeling or sensation associated with these three: physical arousal, conscious experience and behavioral expression.

The body, mind and face are all important in the expression of emotions [4]. According to '**Kleinginna**' emotion is a complex interaction between real world events and our interpersonal feelings about them [4]. Emotions that are generally considered to be emotions such as excitement, happiness or unhappiness also cause physiological changes in the body, such as an increase in heart rate. The combination of all these factors results in a behavior that manifests itself externally. Emotions in Western psychology are generally divided into three categories. Physical Motivations (Primary Motivations), Psychological Motivations (Motivations in General) and acquired Motivations (Social Origin Motivations).

The psychologist "**Munn**" called these personal social motives, and the psychologist Morgan made two points about motives: acquired intentions and non-acquired intentions. Although it is difficult to define emotions precisely, some of its basic features are identified. Emotion is the state of feeling, which is felt in any part or part of the body. As well as, emotions are physiologically based [11].

The emotions that arise in an organism's sexual desire are related to sexual arousal, and through all of these traits, psychoanalysis can be identified by several psychologists in Western psychology as evolving as personal, emotional,

motivational response to physiological and psychological intentions. 'Rosert Plutchik' recognizes it as an emotional cycle [4].

According to him, there are eight basic human emotions. Joy, happiness, fear, sadness, disgust and anger are the primary emotions and love, obedience, wonder, despair, remorse, disgust, aggression, and optimism are the secondary emotions. He is of the opinion that one experiences secondary emotions by being involved. 'Plutchik' believes in having four measurements of emotion. 1- Emotions can be positive or negative, 2- Emotions exist as basic emotions or mixed ones, 3- Most emotions are at opposite ends of the spectrum, 4- Emotions vary in intensity. Thus (Plutchik) sees the mind as an innate reaction, and in the classification of emotions it is identified through two aspects:

1) Positive emotions

2) Negative emotions [4]

Negative emotions include anxiety, anger, sadness, hatred. Jealousy, passionate, love, desire, and curiosity are also referred to as positive emotions. Positive emotions boost a person's self-esteem, affect their ability to interact successfully in the environment in which they live, and help them to see and practice positive behaviours.

Emotions in Buddhism

The concept of emotion as expressed in Buddhism can be simply described as the movement that takes place within a person's psyche for the word emotion. The term 'emotion' is foreign to the Buddhist dialect and is a rare term. It is the new Sinhala term used in the English language study 'Emotion'. A similar usage to the words used for this in Western psychology is not found in Buddhist psychology. However, the English word "Emotion" can be used to refer to the good and the bad from a Buddhist point of view. To look at them from a Buddhist perspective is a philosophy that teaches psychological ethics, and the ethical basis is a special feature of the Buddhist interpretation of emotions.

Buddhism considers positive and negative emotions on a religious perspective. When describing mental functioning, the priority is given to the classifications that are based on the positive and negative aspects of the mental development. Buddhism focuses on emotions from a different perspective than modern psychology, that is, from a moral point of view. Western psychology discusses it in an abstract form of evaluation, consisting of a glossary of terms and contextual facts. Instead of comparing the similarities and differences are between the concepts of western psychology and Buddhist teachings on emotions.

'Liam Lyons' means that every emotion has a certain rating and that rating should be either positive or negative [12]. But in Buddhist interpretation, when the mind functions as an organ, the term '**Dhamma**' is commonly used to describe the purposes for which it is derived, without distinction between positive and negative, and the term also covers emotions [13].

In the analysis of **Abhidhamma**, it is seen that the mental states which are identified as emotions are classified as positive (merit) and negative (demerit). There is a standard analysis of the mind and thoughts. In **Abhidhamma**, it is explained that there is an inseparable connection between the mind and the **Chētasika** being born together, opposing each other and taking one goal, (ēkuppada nirōdhāca – ēkālambana vatthukā, cētō yuttā dvipaṇṇāca – dhammā cētasikā matā) [14].

Buddhism seeks to point out different aspects of emotions through different genres and categories, presenting various situations. The attitude that Buddhism presents emotionally is simply similar to the interpretations of modern psychology and can sometimes be seen to go even further than those views. Buddhism actively seeks not only to analyse those emotions but also to examine them from an ethical point of view. Buddhism can be identified as a religion that erupts into psychological ethics. In the Buddhist interpretation of emotions, from an ethical point of view, emotions are categorized as positive emotions and negative emotions. Buddhism in the West has focused on psychology from a different perspective than modern psychology, that is, from a moral point of view. Buddhism simply values emotion because it accepts all the doctrines of the mind. It is remarkable that the various facets of the emotion are interpreted in such a way that the mental flow flows as a metaphorical process.

Emotion Intelligence

While people experience emotions, these experiences produce a variety of effect in them. But all people do not act in same manner at the same emotional situation. There is a variety of dealing with emotion in people. How to deal with emotions is a skill of intelligence and Peter Salovey and Shone Mayer call such skill as "emotional intelligence" [15] many elements contribute to emotion intelligence and some of the most important skill of emotion intelligence are self-awareness, empathy and understanding emotions [16].

Emotional intelligence has been conceptualized as a multidimensional construct as proposed by Goleman (1995, 1998) and Mayer and Salovey (1990) [17]. According to this conceptualization, emotional intelligence consists of abilities such as being able to motivate one and persist in the face of frustrations; to control impulses and delay gratification; to regulate one's moods and keep distress from swamping the ability to think; to empathize and to hope. Further research in this area has indicated that an emotionally intelligent person is likely to be skilled in two key areas within one's emotional competence framework, namely personal competence how one manages the self, and social competence how one manages relationships. While the former essentially implies self-awareness (of internal states, preferences, resources, and inhibitions), self-regulation (of internal states, impulses and resources, and motivation (traits that facilitate accomplishing goals), the later comprises empathy (the ability to understand other's emotions, and other's talents or skills needed to influence, communicate, lead, develop others, manage conflicts, promote team work or catalysis change), and social skills such as expertise in inculcating desirable responses in others [17]. Thus, emotional intelligence is made up of a set of skills and these skills can be improved through education. Schools serve as the prime location for the promotion of emotional intelligence. Goleman considered school as one place which can turn to compensate children's deficiencies in emotional and social competence. As such schools face the challenge to teaching as well as nurturing the emotional skills of children.

Emotional intelligence describes the ability, capacity, skill, or self-perceived ability to identify, assess, and manage the emotions of one's self, of others, and of groups. People who possess a high degree of emotional intelligence know themselves very well and are also able to sense the emotions of others. They are affable, resilient and optimistic. Surprisingly, emotional intelligence is a relatively recent behavioural model: it was not until the publication of *Emotional Intelligence: why it can matter more than IQ* by Daniel Goleman that the term became popular.

Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to perceive, control and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while others claim it is an inborn characteristic. Since 1990, Peter Salovey and John D. Mayer have been the leading researchers on emotional intelligence. In their influential article "Emotional Intelligence", they defined emotional intelligence as "the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions" (Subramanyam, 2012: 05).

Emotional Management

Emotional intelligence quotient (EQ) embraces two aspects of intelligence: 1-understanding yourself, your goals, intentions, responses, behaviour and all, 2-understanding others, and their feelings [18]. Goleman identified the five 'domains' of EQ as: 1-identifying emotions, 2-managing own emotions, 3-motivating your-self, 4-recognizing and understanding other people's emotions, 5-managing relationships, for an example, managing the emotions of others [18].

Emotional Intelligence embraces and draws from numerous other branches of behavioural, emotional and communications theories, such as NLP (Neuro-Linguistic Programming), Transactional analysis, and empathy. By developing our Emotional Intelligence in these areas and the five EQ domains we can become more productive and successful at what we do, and help others to be more productive and successful too. The process and outcomes of emotional intelligence development also contain many elements known to reduce stress for individuals and

organizations, by decreasing conflict, improving relationships and understanding, and increasing stability, continuity and harmony.

Salovey and Mayer proposed a model that identified four different factors of emotional intelligence: the perception of emotion, the ability reason using emotions, the ability to understand emotion and the ability to manage emotions; **Perceiving Emotion, Using emotions to facilitate thought, Understanding Emotions and Managing Emotions.** Emotions often can be managed. A person needs to understand emotions convey information. To the extent that it is under voluntary control, a person may want to remain open to emotional signals so long as they are not too painful, and block out those that are overwhelming. In between, within the person's emotional comfort zone, it becomes possible to regulate and manage one's own and others' emotions so as to promote one's own and others' personal and social goals. The means and methods for emotional self-regulation has become a topic of increasing research in this decade. According to Salovey and Mayer, the four branches of their model are, "arranged from more basic psychological processes to higher, more psychologically integrated processes. For example, the lowest level branch concerns the (relatively) simple abilities of perceiving and expressing emotion. In contrast, the highest level branch concerns the conscious, reflective regulation of emotion" [19].

Individuals have different personalities, wants, needs, and ways of showing their emotions. Navigating through this requires tact and shrewdness-especially if one hopes to succeed in life. This is where emotional intelligence theory helps. In the most generic framework, five domains of emotional intelligence cover together, they are: **Self-Awareness, Self - Management, Social Awareness, Relationship Management and Social Skills** [20].

Self - Management - Management is your ability to use the awareness of your emotions to stay flexible and direct behaviour positively. This second step is to regulate feelings and manage them so they do more good, both to yourself and others, than harm. Our passions can be contagious and energize others, but our ranting and raving can damage work relations beyond repair. When we get mad, we often sound more upset than we really are because we're allowing raw emotions to surface unchecked. Checking those emotions is what self-regulation is all about. It's giving the rational side of the brain time to catch up and temper our feelings when needed. The goal is to learn how to act intentionally, rather than reactively. When we strive to be intentional, we mean what we say rather than spouting off without thinking and later regretting the impulsive act. When emotions run strong, it is best to slow down and think before moving forward.

Self-control, trustworthiness, conscientiousness and adaptability are components of self - management. Self-managing skills help us to move beyond this victim perspective and "reframe" stressful situations into ones that are challenging and doable. Knowing and managing our own "emotional triggers" is critical to this step.

One important thing to remember in the self-managing step is the effect of self-talk. The manner in which we talk to ourselves during emotional issues is very revealing. What we tell ourselves goes immediately into our subconscious where it increases or decreases our anger and other emotions. 'Repeated negative self-talk' leads to exaggerated and irrational thinking. Some people benefit from using positive affirmations to counter the negative self-talk in their heads.

Relationship Management - Mastering the abilities of self-awareness, self-management, and social awareness pave the way for more effective relationships. This fourth component, relationship management, is about interacting with people and being adept at managing emotions in others. Here are the components: **influence, communication, conflict management, collaboration and cooperation** [21].

Principles of Emotional Management

The fundamental principles of emotional management emphasize their significance in personal and professional life, for instance; mindfulness, cognitive reappraisal and emotional expression. Practicing mindfulness involves being fully present and aware of one's emotions without judgment [22]. For example, in a stressful work situation, a mindful approach would entail acknowledging one's stress and addressing it constructively. Cognitive reappraisal is the process

of reframing one's thoughts to change the emotional response to a situation [23]. In a personal example, if someone receives critical feedback at work, they can reframe it as an opportunity for growth rather than as a personal failure. Openly expressing emotions in an appropriate manner can be cathartic and promote understanding in relationships. For instance, sharing one's fears or concerns with a partner can lead to a deeper emotional connection. Various techniques and tools can aid in emotional management, including meditation [24], journaling [22], and therapy [23]. These strategies empower individuals to gain control over their emotions and foster well-being.

Challenges in emotional management may include cultural influences, individual differences, and situational factors [25]. Cultural norms, for instance, can dictate how emotions are expressed, and recognizing these differences is crucial for effective communication and emotional regulation. Cultural variations impact emotional expression and regulation. For instance, in some cultures, displaying anger may be considered inappropriate, leading individuals to suppress their emotions [26]. Awareness of these cultural nuances is vital in multicultural environments.

In the book '**Practicable guide to manage Emotions**' [2], a number of tools to managing emotions are provided. They are categorised into two sections, the first is environment preparation and the second behavioural techniques to minimize negative emotional effects. It is brought out in appendix 02.

Theravada Jataka Stories

Theravada Buddhism, the oldest surviving school of Buddhism, is rooted in the fundamental teachings of Siddhartha Gautama, the historical Buddha [27]. At its core, Theravada Buddhism emphasizes the pursuit of personal liberation, or arahantship, through meditation, ethical conduct, and the realization of the Four Noble Truths and the Eightfold Path [28]. The ultimate goal is to break free from the cycle of suffering and rebirth, known as samsara. In stark contrast to Theravada's emphasis on individual salvation, the Mahayana tradition introduced the concept of the Bodhisattva [29]. A Bodhisattva is an enlightened being who postpones their own enlightenment or liberation from samsara, to help all sentient beings attain enlightenment. This concept of the Bodhisattva represents a significant shift in focus from personal liberation to the altruistic path of compassion and service to others. **Jataka stories** are centered on the Bodhisattva, the future Buddha, in his previous lives before attaining enlightenment [30]. Through the exploration of these tales, here it aims to highlight their significance within Theravada Buddhism, discuss their content, and extract the moral lessons they convey.

The Role and Significance of Theravada Jataka Stories

Jataka stories play a central role within Theravada Buddhism. They serve as valuable tools for conveying moral and ethical teachings to followers [31]. The term "Jataka" means "birth" and refers to the stories of the Buddha's previous lives before he reached his final incarnation as Siddhartha Gautama [30]. These stories offer a window into the Buddha's moral and spiritual development over countless lifetimes. Around 550 stories are identified in Theravada Jataka collection.

The significance of Jataka stories lies in their ability to illustrate moral principles through narrative. They provide examples of virtuous conduct and offer guidance on how to navigate the complexities of life. For Theravada Buddhists, Jataka stories serve as a source of inspiration and instruction, shaping their ethical and spiritual beliefs [32]. Jataka stories are deeply interwoven with the historical and cultural fabric of Theravada Buddhist communities. They are recited and revered in temples, monasteries, and homes, allowing individuals to connect with the Buddha's journey through lifetimes [33]. These stories contribute to the preservation of Buddhist traditions, acting as both a historical record and a moral compass for practitioners.

The Nature of Jataka Stories

Jataka stories possess distinctive qualities that make them a cherished component of Theravada Buddhism. They are, at their essence, didactic and narrative in nature. Here, we explore the inherent characteristics of these stories:

Didactic Nature: Jataka stories are fundamentally instructive. "Each narrative is carefully constructed to teach specific moral and ethical lessons" [34]. Through the actions and choices of the Bodhisatta in his various incarnations, these stories provide guidance on virtuous conduct and ethical behavior.

Narrative Structure: Jataka stories are presented as engaging narratives. They describe the situations and challenges faced by the Bodhisattva in each life, often involving dilemmas and moral choices [35]. This narrative structure allows for relatable storytelling and helps convey complex moral principles in an accessible way.

Settings, Characters, and Moral Dilemmas: Jataka stories are set in a diverse range of circumstances, including human and animal realms, where the Bodhisattva takes on various forms [33]. The characters, including animals, humans, gods, and celestial beings, interact in these narratives. Moral dilemmas and ethical challenges are common themes, highlighting the importance of making virtuous choices.

The Role of the Bodhisattva: The central character in Jataka stories is the Bodhisattva, the future Buddha [36]. In each story, the Bodhisattva demonstrates qualities such as compassion, selflessness, wisdom, and ethical conduct. The actions and choices of the Bodhisattva serve as exemplars for practitioners to emulate in their own lives.

In conclusion, Jataka stories in Theravada Buddhism are rich in content and serve as a unique medium for imparting moral and ethical teachings. Their didactic nature, narrative structure, and the character of the Bodhisattva all contribute to their significance as a source of guidance and inspiration for Theravada Buddhists. These stories encapsulate the timeless wisdom of the Buddha and continue to shape the moral and ethical landscape of Theravada Buddhist communities.

Emotional Management in Jataka stories

Theravada Jataka stories are a rich source of moral and emotional teachings in Buddhism. These narratives often depict characters facing emotional trials, providing insight into the principles of emotional management and personal growth. They deeply rooted in Buddhist tradition, offer valuable insights into human emotions and the principles of emotional management. These narratives not only provide moral and ethical teachings but also illustrate the complexities of human emotions and how they can be managed in the pursuit of enlightenment. The Jataka tales often present emotional challenges and dilemmas faced by the characters, reflecting the human condition and the intricate interplay of emotions. These stories serve as a platform for understanding and managing emotions effectively. For instance, **equanimity, resilience, compassion, emotional regulation, detachment** and **contentment** are important emotional managing principles Jataka tales promote.

Many Jataka stories emphasize emotional equanimity in the face of adversity. For example, in the tale of "The Wise Hare" (Mahahamsa Jataka) [37], a clever hare displays resilience and emotional composure when faced with a life-threatening situation. In the "Mahahamsa Jataka," the wise hare's ability to remain calm and composed when facing danger illustrates the principle of emotional equanimity. This equanimity allows the hare to outwit the lion and save its life.

Jataka stories often highlight the significance of compassion and emotional regulation. In the story of "The Grateful Elephant" (Nalagiri Jataka) (Ken, Visakha Kawasaki, Simon and Schuster, 2006), the Buddha's compassion transforms an aggressive and intoxicated elephant, showcasing the power of emotional regulation through kindness. The "Nalagiri Jataka" demonstrates the transformative power of compassion. The Buddha's act of kindness towards an aggressive elephant not only saves lives but also illustrates the importance of emotional regulation and the positive impact of compassion.

Detachment and contentment are central themes in emotional management. "The Story of the Golden Goose" (Suvannahsna Jataka) [37] teaches the value of contentment and warns against the perils of greed, illustrating the principle of detachment from material possessions. In the "Suvannahsna Jataka," the story of the golden goose underscores the principle of detachment. It conveys the message that contentment and detachment from material possessions lead to inner peace and emotional stability.

Method

Materials and Variables

Here we randomly selected 50 stories of Theravada Buddhist Jataka collection from “The book of five hundred and fifty Jataka tales” [3], and it is a summarized translation into Sinhala (Sri Lankan language) from Pali language. They are well compared with Pali Jataka commentary and other Sinhala resources. As psychological tools we analysed the process model of emotion regulation [39], the model of emotional intelligence [19] and the third chapter of the book ‘**Practicable guide to manage Emotions**’ [2]. Kumarasena’s book provides a number of principles to managing emotions, and they are categorised into two sections called as ‘A’ (background preparation) and ‘B’ (behavioural techniques to reduce negative emotional effects). As well as, we focused on previous researches on the related subject matter mentioned in literature review and they were supportive to recognize the research gap. The independent variable is ‘Theravada Jataka stories’ and the dependent variable is ‘emotional management principles’.

Procedure

Having based on literature resources this study was conducted. The primary resource was 50 of Jataka stories of Theravada Buddhism (appendix 1) and emotional managing techniques of Kumarasena’s book (appendix 2). And secondary information is gathered from multiple psychological and Buddhist text books, previous research papers and internet. Data from Buddhist resources and psychological models are compared in how emotions are managed in these tales.

Specially, we arranged how each of principles (appendix 2) has represented from evidences of analysed stories. Techniques (appendix 2) are here classified into two major sections; ‘A’ (preparing background) and ‘B’ (general behavioural patterns to minimize negative emotional effects). Kumarasena’s book has numbered these principles as 14 sub-topics of section ‘A’, and 10 of section ‘B’. Therefore, in this investigation we analyzed individually each of stories according to these sub-themes. And finally the conclusion of research hypothesis is done based on the correlation of variables.

Results

After all information has been collected, I highlighted which of emotional management principles has been appeared in each of Jajaka stories, and calculated the percentages by amount of those principles. The row data and a description of the analyses can be found as following tables. These tables are present the numbers of two section in Kumarasena’s book.

Table 01; Section A. Preparation of the background

Number of EM principles	Represented Jataka Stories	%
A.1.1	16	32
A.1.2	17	34
A.2.1	30	60
A.2.2	18	36
A.3.1.1	12	24
A.3.1.2	14	28
A.3.2.1	06	12
A.3.2.2	03	06
A.3.3.1	04	08
A.3.3.2	09	18

A.4.1	05	10
A.4.2	11	22
A.4.3	03	06

Table 02; Section B. General behavioural patterns to minimize effects of negative emotions.

Number of EM principles	Represented Jataka Stories	%
B.1	25	50
B.2	25	50
B.3	04	08
B.4	16	32
B.5	07	14
B.6	02	04
B.7	04	08
B.8	04	08
B.9	05	10
B.10	18	36

These tables show the averages in two conditions. As predicted, the stories' evidences has covered each sub-themes of emotional managing techniques related both sections themselves. The number of items frequently identified within these tales.

Example 1:

A.1.1) Do not visit such places

For avoiding facing situations, that could cause emotional responses, prevention of visiting such palaces are symptoms in this criteria and it represents within Sixteen jataka stories; *Kandina, Vatamiga, Baka, Kapota, Litta, Suvarna hansa, Udancanee, Singala-1, Pushparatna, Singala-2, Samiddhi, Gahapati, Vikannika, Asatamanta, Kuragga and Sujata* [3].

Example 2:

A.1.2) Prepare the environment to overcome such triggering situations.

Seventeen Jataka tales has uncovered evidence of this technique according to the present study. They are *Devadharm, Sukha vihari, Kandina, Mahilamukha, Nandivisala, Kapota, Cullajanaka, Litta, Durvalakasta, Udancanee, Godha, Asatamanta, Mahamantu, Madupani, Kuragga, Vatasaindava* and *Sujata* [3].

Example 3:

A.2.1) Be aware of the mood that is likely to generate negative emotional reaction, under specific condition.

It extrapolates thirty observed stories match with the third principle in Kumarasena's book. Stories; *Serivaniya, Makhadeva, Devadharm, Sukha vihari, Kandina, Nandivisala, Cullajanaka, Durajana, Saketa, Bahiya, Litta, Telapatta, Durvalakasta, Udancanee, Vattaka, Bandana mokkha, Uranga, Singala-2, Asatamanta, Duta, Paduma, Cullapalobhana, Kuragga, Vatasaindava* and *Sujata* etc. [3] lead to realize disturbing emotional situations. And it displays as a cognitive reappraisal technique at supervision of such emotions.

Example 4:

A.2.2) Cultivate resisting mechanism in advance, to change the mood to a more favourable mood.

Eighteen stories; *Serivaniya, Makhadeva, Devadharm, Mahilamukha, Cullajanaka, Saketa, Litta, Durvalakasta, Vattaka, Uranga, Asatamanta, Cullapalobhana, Kuragga, Vatasaindava* and *Sujata* etc. [3] suggest emotional practises similar to this strategy.

These features give the significant relationship between Jataka stories and emotional managing tools in Kumarasena's book. It can be interpreted as there is a strong correlation between two variables of the study, and the data is enough to prove the hypothesis of the current research.

Discussion

My study's purpose was to investigate the psychological emotional managing principles available in Theravada Jataka stories and to suggest that by following them people can improve skills to enhance emotional intelligence. Above result showed in this study supports to conclude these aims.

The emotional principles found in the Jataka stories continue to be relevant in modern life. They provide a framework for managing emotions, fostering compassion, and achieving inner peace in a world filled with emotional challenges and distractions. And they serve as a timeless source of emotional management principles, highlighting the importance of equanimity, compassion, and detachment. These narratives provide valuable insights for individuals seeking emotional balance and personal growth.

Effective emotional management offers numerous advantages, such as improved relationships, reduced stress, and better decision-making [26]. When individuals are in control of their emotions, they can respond to challenges more rationally and maintain healthier connections with others. Jataka stories have highly influenced on Buddhist communities in Asia during two thousand and five hundred years. Marteen Wickramasinhe (most famous author in Sri Lanka) says 'having read Jataka collection, someone can achieve living experiences during 500 years'. Promoting and studying Jathaka stories as educational tool is effective method to enhance emotional competency in children as well in adults. Further researches are essential on this field to investigate psychological support of Jataka literature and Bodhisattva concept for the well-being in current communities.

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Appendix 01

List of 50 analysed Jataka stories [3]

01. Serivaniya
02. Makhadeva
03. Devadharmā

04. Sukha vihari
05. Kandina
06. Vatamiga
07. Mahilamukha
08. Nandivisala
09. Baka
10. Nanda
11. Kapota
12. Cullajanaka
13. Durajana
14. Saketa
15. Kuhaka
16. Bahiya
17. Litta
18. Suvarna hansa
19. Telapatta
20. Durvalakasta
21. Udancanee
22. Vattaka
23. Bandana mokkha
24. Panca garuka
25. Singala (1)
26. Godha
27. Uranga
28. Katahaka
29. Ubhatobhatta
30. Pushparatna
31. Singala (2)
32. Samiddhi
33. Araka
34. Gahapati
35. Cullananda
36. Putabhatta
37. Vikannika
38. Kumbhila
39. Vennuthuna
40. Asitabu
41. Salaka
42. Asatamanta
43. Mahamantu
44. Duta
45. Paduma
46. Madupani
47. Cullapalobhana

- 48. Kuragga
- 49. Vatasaindava
- 50. Sujata

Appendix 02

Principles of emotional management; the third chapter of the book Practicable guide to manage Emotions [2]
Section 01;

A. Preparation of the background

A.1.) Avoid facing situations, that could cause emotional responses.

A.1.1) Do not visit such places

A.1.2) Prepare the environment to overcome such triggering situations.

A.2.) Sustain temperaments and moods, that resist negative emotions.

A.2.1) Be aware of the mood that is likely to generate negative emotional reaction, under specific condition.

A.2.2) Cultivate resisting mechanism in advance, to change the mood to a more favourable mood.

A.3.) Minimize the chances of having Emotions, when such situations cannot be avoided.

A.3.1) Manage Emotions related input data streams.

A.3.1.1- Do not allow input mechanisms to generate streams of data can match the relevant past experiences.

A.3.1.2- Skill related to modification of input mechanism to accommodate this property should be practiced in day to day life.

A.3.2) Managing the reappearance of Emotions, while receiving the same type of information.

A.3.2.1- Focus on the action of accepting the input data, without changing the attention to understand the nature of data.

A.3.2.2- Skill of focusing on actions should be practiced daily life.

A.3.3) Managing Emotions created due to physical pain.

A.3.3.1- Focus on the place of the body, where pain is present, rather than on the pain itself.

A.3.3.2- skill should be developed while engaged in daily activities.

A.4.) After emotion has taken the control, minimize its harmful effects.

A.4.1) Avoid taking actions until the refractory period is over.

A.4.2) Switch the mind to an experience that generates pleasant experience.

(Those who have gathered spiritual experiences can shift the attention to a spiritual experience that provides inspiration.)

A.4.3) Attempt to change facial expressions to reflect a more pleasant emotion.

Section 02;

B. General behavioural patterns that should be cultivated to minimize the overall effects of negative emotions.

B.1.) To acquire knowledge related to emotions, their background and probable reasons.

B.2.) To develop awareness to detect the early stages of emotional response, this enables to act fast.

B.3.) Since facial expression reflects the nature of emotion, by propagating friendly thoughts about others will minimize effects of negative triggers from others.

B.4.) To select the environment, associates, vocation etc. that minimize the events that leads to negative emotions.

B.5.) Adopt necessary lifestyle changes. Lead simple life.

B.6.) Maintain good physical health.

B.7.) Devote time for relaxation (Meditations).

B.8.) Associate spiritual companions or groups who are willing and prepared to help and support when need arises.

B.9.) keep records of negative emotional reactions.

B.10.) To implement planned actions to help others, especially children, to minimize their negative emotions.

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